

IN-HABIT – INclusive Health And wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies

D6.1 – Behavioural Games for Preference

Elicitation

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PARTNERS' SHORT NAMES

AVUE	Neighbourhood Association of Las Palmeras
BOT	Book on a Tree
BSC	Baltic Studies Centre
B4B	Bridge for Billions
CORD	Ayuntamiento de Córdoba
DFC	Design for Change Spain
HIDE	Hidepark Civic Association Triptych
ISIM	isIMPACT
KQ	Kalneciema Quarter
LABORELEC	Engie Laborelec
LCREA	Lucca Crea
LUCCA	Comune di Lucca
NITRA	Mesto Nitra
PUJ	Pontificia Universidad Javeriana
RIGA	Riga Planning Region
SUA	Slovak University of Agriculture in Nitra

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TSR	Tesserae
UCO	University of Córdoba
UNIPI	Università di Pisa
UREAD	University of Reading
WTG	WellnessTechGroup

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In IN-HABIT, each city aims to improve health and well-being using different solutions. Each of the envisioned solutions can be considered as common-pool resources which will deplete if they are not properly managed by citizens. We have designed and run experiments with the aim to elicit and understand social preferences, particularly willingness to cooperate and contribute to a common pool resource in each of the four different cities. This document reports the results of the first phase of public good experiments.

Public good experiments are a type of economic experiment that investigates individuals' behaviour in situations where they can contribute to a public good. The classic public goods game involves participants deciding how much of their resources to contribute to a common pool, with the option to free-ride and benefit from others' contributions without contributing themselves.

In our design, participants are placed in the context of investing into a common-pool resource as part of a group of 5 participants. They are given a fixed endowment of 100 tokens, from which they have to decide how much to contribute to the common-pool resource. Whatever goes into the common pool from each contributor is multiplied and then split equally among group members irrespective of the amount contributed. At the end, individuals' final pay-off is the sum of what they kept and the equal share of the common-pool resource. The game is repeated for three rounds, whereby, in the second and third round, participants take into consideration what other participants have contributed in previous rounds. This allows us to assess whether the willingness to contribute to a common pool evolves over time as participants are aware of what others have contributed to: do they follow what others have done, do they compensate for a depleting common pool, or do they behave regardless of what others' contribution has been in previous rounds?

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Each city then selected one of their solutions to be the basis of the context for their respective game. More specifically, Cordoba (WP1) chose a multifunctional green space, Riga (WP2) chose a community stage, Lucca (WP3) chose Animal-Assisted Interventions, and Nitra (WP4) chose a picnic meadow. Moreover, we aim to assess whether cooperation would differ if the common-pool resource would have more targeted beneficiaries, such as vulnerable groups, rather than be seen as beneficial just to the general public as whole. Each city identified a vulnerable group in line with the local context: Cordoba chose Las Palmeras residents (socio-economic background), Riga chose sexual minorities, Lucca chose the elderly and Nitra chose Roma people.

Overall, across all cities, we find that the average contribution to a common pool is quite high, around 75, compared to what is usually known (around 50) for this kind of experiment. Moreover, there is a general decreasing pattern of individual contributions with the level of the group contribution. The lower the group contribution, the fewer participants contribute. So, on average, participants are conditional cooperators and tend to punish free-riders. But this behaviour does not depend on the identity of the beneficiary of the common-pool resources as both treatment groups exhibit this same pattern.

Across all cities, although there does not seem to be general differences between participants depending on the identity of the beneficiary of the common-pool resources, we can notice differences when group participants are contributing the least (stages 2c, 3d and 3e). Participants contribute more in this situation when the common-pool resource benefits the vulnerable group than when the common-pool resource benefits the general population. They still decrease their contribution compared to higher group contributions, but much less than when common-pool resources benefit the general population.

Always across cities, when looking at differences by gender, men and women behave very differently. Women tend to reduce their contribution less than men when the contribution of others decreases. Men, on the contrary, tend to reduce their contribution when the group

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contributions are the highest. It could be that men either favour their own interest and free-ride if there is a good opportunity to do so, or that they decide to step aside if the common-pool resource already gets a large support.

That being said, there are relevant differences in overall contributions, gender gaps and strategic behaviours between the four cities. For instance, considering overall contributions, in Riga and Cordoba, the contribution to the common pool is overall higher when this benefits the general population rather than the specific vulnerable group; in Lucca it is the opposite, while in Nitra there is overall no difference and participants to the experiment contribute overall the same amount whether the project benefits the general population or the targeted vulnerable group. We also found a range of different gender gaps in willingness to contribute in the four cities, which we report in detail in the Results section of this report.

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1. Introduction

IN-HABIT is a Horizon 2020 research project on inclusive health and well-being in four small and medium size European cities funded by the European Commission. Each city develops new solutions in four dimensions to foster inclusive health and well-being. Cordoba (Spain) uses culture and heritage to promote inclusivity. Riga (Latvia) mobilises food to nurture daily healthier lifestyles. Lucca (Italy) promotes human-animal bonds as new relational urban goods. Finally, Nitra (Slovakia) works with art and environment to connect places and people. Each city focuses its action on deprived areas and vulnerable groups such as children, elders, women, persons with disability, ethnic minorities and migrants.

A distinct approach of the programme is to consider health and well-being as a common pool resource (CPR), created, managed and used by the community but affected by low excludability and high subtractability. Common pool resources are shared and available to everyone but are also scarce, with a finite supply. This makes them susceptible to exploitation and diminished availability if individuals pursue their own self-interest. Moreover, if individuals and groups' social interests are in conflict - for instance they may have different willingness to cooperate and participate in the management of the resource - then they would clearly be incentives for users to ignore the social costs. Moreover, lack of shared ideas, values, incentives between individuals or groups of individuals are typically associated with lower trust, therefore potentially with higher costs of negotiation and bargaining and different motivations to cooperate.

These issues have traditionally engaged economists who attempted to find solutions to how to finance a public good, a good for which the market would not exist and which could be financed either by taxation or by voluntary contributions. This would pose important problems: what would happen if a public goods were indeed sought to be provided through voluntary contributions? Would individuals make enough contributions to cover the cost of the public good? Self-interested individuals would typically free ride and the total amount collected via voluntary contributions mechanism (VCM) would be zero. Experiments have been designed

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and employed to shed light on these issues and test the sustainability of collective action since the late 1970s. More specifically, the experiments make use of so-called public good games, namely stylised models of situations that require cooperation to achieve socially beneficial outcomes in the presence of free-rider incentives. There are very many examples in the real world where such situations are cogent, including voting, paying taxes, fighting corruption, contributing to public goods, teamwork, work morale, neighbourhood watch, common pool resource management, recycling, tackling climate change, and so on. These are frequent situations with the common feature that cooperation leads to a group- beneficial outcome but is jeopardised by selfish incentives to ride free on others' contributions.

Cooperation is a cornerstone of sustainable behaviours. Humans thrive and overcome crises because they are able to cooperate. From the first hunter-gatherers, specialising and sharing resources, to nowadays democracies, cooperation has been essential to regulate social interactions and manage public goods. In the more recent past, the vast majority cooperated to protect the health of everyone during the COVID-19 pandemic. But cooperation is fragile. For instance, anti-vax individuals, by refusing to get vaccinated, undermined the effort to build collective immunity. Hence, even the actions of relatively small groups may undermine cooperation and trap societies in undesirable situations.

Cooperation may be at risk because individuals have different preferences for public goods. It is explicit in elections where voters favour some political platforms over others. In this case, individuals may not contribute enough for the public good to be financed, which may result in no public good being delivered at all. But, it might also be that individuals would prefer to contribute less, or not contribute at all, when the common good, resource or activity is shared with individuals from a different social group, however this is identified. For instance, Alesina et al. (1999) demonstrated that individuals tend to favour less investment in public goods when these public goods are also benefiting minority groups. Anti-migrants policies or segregationist policies are also manifestations of this problem. By excluding one (or more) group(s), social cohesion erodes, reducing support for public goods and increasing the risk of conflict.

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In IN-HABIT, each city aims to improve health and well-being using different solutions. Each of the envisioned solutions can be considered as common-pool resources which will deplete if they are not properly managed by citizens. In order to address potential issues associated with the management of CPR, therefore, IN-HABIT aims to develop and implement behavioural games in two distinct phases: the first aims to elicit and understand social preferences -particularly willingness to cooperate and contribute to a common pool resource in each of the different cities; the second aims to test targeted interventions with an equality, diversity and inclusion approach.

This document reports on the first phase of the behavioural games. It presents the methodological approach employed to design the behavioural games and presents and discusses the results of the experiments carried out in the four cities of the IN-HABIT programme.

The report is structured as follows. In Section 2 we review the main literature on public good experiments; in Section 3 we describe the design of the experiments we conduct in the four cities. In Sections 4 and 5 we present the data and the results of the analysis respectively. We then draw main conclusions and discussion in Section 6.

2. Literature review

Many researchers have focused on studying the behavioural mechanisms involved in the exploitation of resources but also more particularly in the case of common pool resources (CPRs).

Public good experiments are a type of economic experiment that investigates individuals' behaviour in situations where they can contribute to a public good. The classic public goods game involves participants deciding how much of their resources to contribute to a common pool, with the option to free-ride and benefit from others' contributions without contributing themselves. The standard linear public goods experiment using VCM is played in a classroom

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or a computer laboratory where participants are anonymously put in small groups. They are given an endowment and asked to divide the endowment to a private account (which they get to keep) and a public account for the public good or common pool resource. After all participants decide, the amount in the public account is added up, multiplied by a factor, and divided equally among the members of the group. Thus total individual earnings is the sum of the amount the participant did not contribute to the public account plus the share received from the public account. It is easy to see that a person's best strategy (defined as NAsH equilibrium) would be to contribute nothing to the common pool, while the socially optimal solution (the one that would be preferable from society's perspective) would be to contribute the entire endowment. This kind of public goods experiments are typically repeated over several rounds and an endowment is provided at the beginning of each round.

Since the original experiments in the late 1970s (Marwell and Ames, 1979), there has been an explosion of such experiments in this framework, including a very large variety of treatments and designs, in a range of contexts and settings. It is impossible to detail all the evidence in this report, so we will first summarise key conclusions from the evidence and then focus on one particular study (Hermann et al, 2008) because it included public good experiments in 16 countries around the World, representing therefore different context and cultures and providing underlying evidence for most of the key conclusions.

Overall, the following points can be made about the overall evidence from public good experiments:

Conditional Cooperation: Many experiments show that people are often willing to contribute to public goods, especially when they believe others will contribute as well. This suggests a level of conditional cooperation, where individuals are more likely to contribute if they expect others to do the same.

Punishment and Norms: The introduction of punishment mechanisms or social norms can significantly impact cooperation levels. Punishment can act as a deterrent to free-riding and enhance overall contributions to public goods.

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Cultural Differences: Studies have explored how cultural factors influence behaviour in public good games. Cultural norms, values, and societal structures can shape individuals' willingness to cooperate and contribute to public goods.

Institutional Design: The design of institutions and rules can have a substantial impact on cooperation. For example, experiments have examined how the introduction of communication, the ability to sanction free-riders, or changes in the payoff structure can influence behaviour.

Temporal Dynamics: The dynamics of contributions to public goods over time have been explored. Some studies suggest that contributions tend to decline over time, especially without mechanisms in place to sustain cooperation.

Heterogeneity: Individual differences, such as personality traits or economic preferences, can influence contributions to public goods. Some people may be more altruistic or more inclined to cooperate than others.

Figure 1 shows the result of a public good experiment conducted with more than 1100 university students in 16 cities across the World, from Boston in the USA to Copenhagen, Athens and Zurich in Europe, Muscat and Riyadh in the Arab region, Chengdu and Seoul in Asia and Melbourne in Australia, amongst others (Hermann et al, 2008). Each line corresponds to the average contribution, over ten rounds, of participants from a different location around the world. The figure shows that individuals are not solely self-interested: if they were, and reasoned that everyone else was also self-interested, then they would not contribute.

In every city where the game was played, there must have been a substantial fraction of people with social preferences. Contributions to the public good were high in the first period, although much more so in some cities (Copenhagen) than in others (Melbourne). The figure also shows another important results from public good experiments:, which indeed underlines the tragedy of the commons and the problems of managing common pool resources: it is difficult to sustain voluntary contribution to the public good. Everywhere in the 16 cities in the experiments, contributions to the public good decreased over time. However, despite a large

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variation across societies, most of them still have high contribution levels at the end of the 10 rounds of the experiment.

The same study also assessed what happened when a punishment option was introduced: after observing the contributions of their group, individuals could pay to punish other individuals by making them pay a fine. The punisher remained anonymous but had also to pay \$1 per individual punished.

Figure 1: Worldwide public goods experiments

Source: Hermann et al, 2008. Figure 3.

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The effect is shown in **Figure 2**. For the majority of subjects, including those in China, South Korea, northern Europe, and the English-speaking countries, contributions increased when they had the opportunity to punish free riders.

Figure 2: Worldwide public goods experiments with peer punishment

Source: Hermann et al, 2008. Figure 2A.

The possibility of maintaining contributions with peer-punishment is also linked to Ostrom’s seminal work, which has shown that CPRs can be successfully and sustainably managed without the intervention of an external authority (Ostrom, 1992; 2000). Running field experiments with real CPR’s users, Ostrom demonstrated that the simple use of communication between resource users can successfully lead groups to achieve higher social outcomes. This also contributed to change what would hitherto have been considered as cheap talk into a possible tool alongside those traditionally proposed by standard economic theories, which emphasised the role of financial incentives.

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In parallel, behavioural economics brings to light the role social preferences may play in explaining how individuals' behaviour may deviate from non socially-optimal outcomes in the context of limited resources. For instance, a series of public good games show that individuals may cooperate under various motives, such as altruism (Andreoni, 1990), reciprocity (Rabin, 1993), peer's approval or disapproval (Gächter and Fehr, 1999), inequity aversion (Fehr and Schmidt, 1999), fairness (Falk et al., 2003), conditional cooperation (Gächter, 2007), but also via social norms (Fehr and Gächter, 2000; Ferraro and Price, 2013). At the sight of this literature, individuals are not purely selfish, but care about others' well-being and could resist inequitable outcomes. They are far from indifferent to their peers' behaviour and individuals tend to respond to cooperative behaviour by being more cooperative and vice versa. Individuals are also looking for social approval and are willing to face costs in order to enforce cooperation within their group. All of these elements reinforce the potential of self-regulation techniques.

Since Ostrom's first CPR game (1994), a number of experimental investigations, both in the field and in the lab, have shown that simple self-governed solution such as face-to-face communication between the resource's users could encompass costly governmental solution (Cárdenas et al., 2004; Vélez et al., 2010; Travers et al., 2011). The first meta-analysis on the impact of communication in social dilemmas was conducted by Sally (1995), who concluded that communication increases cooperation by an average of 40 percent. In a more recent meta-analysis listing experimental evidence, Balliet (2010) reports a large positive effect of communication. He further discusses moderators, showing the importance of the type of communication (face to face discussion being more efficient than written messages) and the size of the group (communication works better in larger groups than smaller ones).

Other research indicates the circumstances under which self-governed solutions may outperform externally driven ones. The primacy (or equivalence) of communication over other means may thus depend on the institutional environment, as cooperation in social dilemma is more likely to be observed when the underlying set of informal norms prevailing in the community is high (Gächter et al., 2010; Volland et al., 2017). In a similar vein, the degree of interaction these communities have with the market may also play a role in the way externally

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versus internally driven solutions will interact with cooperation (Ishiara and Pascual, 2012). Confirming this path dependence pattern, Prediger et al. (2011) find that the success of non-price intervention on cooperation depends on historical institutional development. More specifically, they show that higher cooperation levels were found in communities with a longer experience in cooperative resource management.

3. Design

The general objective of this study is to elicit preferences for public goods and assess the level of cooperation or willingness to contribute to a common good, resource or activity in the four IN-HABIT cities.

The design we employ in our experiments combines a common-pool resources game with a random framing to elicit whether cooperation differs between participants exposed to different framing. The common-pool resources game places participants in the context of investment in public goods where cooperation is essential. Then, adding random framings allows generating different circumstances that may change cooperative behaviours.

In this study, participants are placed in the context of investing into a common-pool resource as part of a group of 5 participants. They will start the game with a fixed endowment of 100 tokens, from which they have to decide how much to contribute to the common-pool resource. Whatever goes into the common pool from each contributors is multiplied and then split equally among group members irrespective of the amount contributed. At the end, individuals' final pay-off is the sum of what they kept and the equal share of the common-pool resource.

As cooperative behaviours may evolve over time, participants will repeat this simple common-pool resources game three times taking into consideration what other participants have contributed in previous rounds. In the first round, participants are given their endowment

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which can later be exchanged at a fixed rate against euros, known to the participants before playing any round. Then, they are asked how much of these 100 tokens they would like to contribute to the common-pool resource. In the second round, participants are again given 100 tokens at the beginning of the round and asked how much they would like to contribute in three potential scenarios, which corresponds to whether other participants of their group are contributing a large, medium, or small amount. Finally, the third round repeats what has been done in the previous round, also considering the level of contributions of the group, which then makes five potential scenarios: group members have contributed a very large, large, medium, small, or very small amount.

Each city then selected one of their solutions to be the basis of the context for their respective game. More specifically, Cordoba (WP1) chose a multifunctional green space, Riga (WP2) chose a community stage, Lucca (WP3) chose Animal-Assisted Interventions, and Nitra (WP4) chose a picnic meadow. All common-pool resources were described in a neutral way (see appendix) and presented as potential projects that could come to life in the near future. This was done to ensure that participants would relate to the projects and would provide genuine answers to the game.

1. Framing

In the context of social experiments, framing consists in manipulating the set of circumstances participants will be exposed to. It could take many different forms such as different information provided about the context or other participants, visual elements in the support of the study, or even different experimenters. Regardless of the form it takes, if individuals are sensitive to the element manipulated by the framing, they should react to it (even unconsciously) and behave differently than individuals exposed to the control framing.

In this project, we aim to assess potential threats to cooperation and, in particular, whether cooperation would differ if the common-pool resource would have more targeted beneficiaries,

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such as vulnerable groups, rather than be seen as beneficial just to the general public as whole. To this respect, we designed two versions of the game. In one (which we call the control version) the project is described as benefiting only the general population; in the other (which we call the treatment version), the project was presented as benefiting a specific vulnerable group as well as the general population. We then randomly assigned the game questionnaires to the participants. If participants are sensitive to the identity of the most likely beneficiary of a common-pool resource, we should expect them to adjust the amount they are willing to contribute to the common-pool resource.

As for the common-pool resources, each city decided on the more appropriate vulnerable group, the one most likely to be at risk of discrimination in their respective context. Cordoba (WP1) chose Las Palmeras residents (socio-economic background), Riga (WP2) chose sexual minorities (sexual orientation), Lucca (WP3) chose the Elderly (age), and Nitra (WP4) chose Roma people (ethnic or social origin).

The exact framings used in each case are described in the Annex.

4. Data and Methods

Participants were recruited by the local teams using all the communication channels at their disposal. In particular, they made extensive use of the network they have built through their IN-HUB. This wide range of recruitment methods allowed to circulate a neutral recruitment call as widely as possible to get a sample of citizens as representative as possible. In the end, 114 participants were involved in Cordoba, 108 in Riga, 121 in Lucca, and 131 in Nitra.

4.1. Assessing cooperation

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To assess the presence of barriers to cooperation, we estimate with Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) the following equation:

$$Contribution_{ri} = \alpha + \beta \cdot Treated_i + \varepsilon_{ri}$$

where $Contribution_{ri}$ is the contribution to the common-pool resource made by individual i during round r ; $Treated_i$ indicates whether individual i was contributing to a common-pool resource that would benefit a vulnerable group ($Treated_i = 1$) or just the general population ($Treated_i = 0$); and ε_{ri} is an error term assumed spherical. β can be directly interpreted as the marginal willingness to contribute when the common-pool resource benefits a vulnerable group. If β is equal to zero, this would be indicative of the absence of barriers to cooperation. If β is positive, then participants would be prone to contribute more when the common-pool resource benefits a vulnerable group than the general population, and conversely if β is negative.

In order to assess potential gender differences in contributions, we estimate with OLS the following equation:

$$Contribution_{ri} = \alpha + \beta_1 \cdot Treated_i + \beta_2 \cdot Gender_i + \beta_3 \cdot Treated_i * Gender_i + \varepsilon_{ri}$$

where $Male_i$ denotes whether individual i is a man ($Gender_i = 1$) or woman ($Gender_i = 0$); and all the other variables are defined as before. In this regression, the parameter β_3 is the main parameter of interest. It directly captures the average gender gap in contribution when the common-pool resource benefits a vulnerable group. Other quantities of interest include: β_1 - the average marginal willingness to contribute among women when the common-pool resource benefits a vulnerable group;

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$\beta_1 + \beta_3$ - the average marginal willingness to contribute among men when the common-pool resource benefits a vulnerable group;

α - the average contribution of women when the common-pool resource benefits the general population;

$\alpha + \beta_1$ - the average contribution of women when the common-pool resource benefits the vulnerable group;

$\alpha + \beta_2$ - the average contribution of men when the common-pool resource benefits the general population;

$\alpha + \beta_1 + \beta_2 + \beta_3$ - the average contribution of men when the common-pool resource benefits the vulnerable group.

We estimate these two regressions separately for each four cities of the project.

4.2. Who are the cooperators

After assessing the levels of cooperation, we are interested in characterising the cooperators and how they cooperate. Participants could contribute in many different ways, ranging from contributing nothing to contributing everything, and they could react very differently to the other participants' contributions, either punishing or compensating for the others, or even doing nothing. These different strategic behaviours convey important information for policy makers about the nature of cooperation, but, if, in addition, specific groups naturally behave in the same way, policies supporting cooperation can then be tailored much more precisely to these particular groups for a possibly greater effect.

The structure of the game is such that participants maximise their own pay-off when they contribute nothing while others are contributing a lot to the common-pool resource. In other words, individuals have incentives to free-ride when others are ensuring the proper management of the common-pool resource. However, since everybody has the same incentive,

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the predicted final outcome (so-called Nash equilibrium) is that nobody contributes to the common-pool resource. This is because whenever someone contributes, if someone else does not, the free-rider gets a share of the premium generated by the common-pool resource in addition to keeping its own money. As no participant alone can make the investment in the common-pool resource beneficial, then free-riding is each individual's dominant strategy, since contributing is less rewarding in terms of individual monetary pay-off: the outcome is that nobody should contribute at all, leading to the predicted tragedy of the commons mentioned above.

This is the predicted outcome if participants are able to see that, conditional on any level of contribution, it is better to free-ride (again, in terms of individual monetary pay-off). However, this strategy is not that obvious to see and pay-offs are still increasing with the level of the group contribution, which individuals can directly increase on their own. So, there exists another possible outcome, alternative to free-riding, where individuals try to maximize the group contribution by investing everything they have. In fact, there is a threshold (500) in the group contribution above which participants will get more (individual monetary pay-off) if they contribute than if no one does.

When considering how behaviours evolve over time, theoretical predictions can be obtained by solving the last iteration and going backward. In this case, it is clear that, if there is no subsequent round, individuals should free-ride in the last round. But if participants expect to free-ride, they should also do so in the previous round. Since there will be no additional contribution in the last round, free-riding on the last round where there could still be contributions is more rewarding. But, since the incentives are the same for every participant, everybody should free-ride in the second round as well. The same logic applies for the same round, and again, the prediction is that everybody should contribute nothing.

However, several dynamic effects may mitigate this prediction. The “carrot-and-stick” strategy, for instance, is fairly common and corresponds to cooperating until someone defects. In this

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case, cooperation may be maintained because participants signal that they are willing to cooperate. If participants are willing to follow and cooperate to some extent, they may be able to get higher monetary pay-offs than if they free-ride.

More generally, all these strategies belong to the class of conditionally cooperative behaviours where the participants' individual strategies are correlated with what others are doing. If positively correlated, participants reduce their contribution if others are also reducing their contribution, whereas if negatively correlated, participants would increase their contribution if others are reducing their contribution.

Overall, we can distinguish three main types of cooperators. First, the unconditional cooperators are those participants who are contributing all their endowment at each stage, regardless of what others are doing. Second, the compensating contributors correspond to those participants that would contribute more if the group contribution decreased. These two groups can be thought of as activists, individuals keen to sustain the common pool resource and activities, the first group regardless of what others do and the second group depending on whether the common pool is at risk, in which case they would step in and compensate for the decreased contributions from others. Third, the conditional cooperators who are followers, in the sense that they would only contribute more if others are contributing more, and would also follow what their group is doing if the group contribution decreased. We group all the participants who do not fit in one of these three categories in another common category that we call "inconsistent behaviours", since it includes strategy profiles that are not clearly categorised in the three descriptions above.

5. Results

5.1. How to read and interpret the figures

In the following subsections we report the results from the public good games in each of the four IN-HABIT cities. We start by presenting the focus of the game in terms of the specific

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public good or common resource or activity and the specific vulnerable group chosen and identified in each specific context. We also briefly describe the sample of participants and some of the key characteristics. We then focus on the results in terms of overall cooperation before proceeding to describe the gender gaps and the main strategic behaviours we have identified.

How to read the figures we report below? For each city, we report three main figures. The first (titles Treatment effects) shows the overall results, the second and third figures report the results by gender (one chart for women and one for men). For each of them, the figure reports, on the vertical axis, the mean contribution, namely the average amount that the respondents are willing to contribute to the common pool. In the horizontal axis, we report this average amount at each of the three stages of the game: the initial, first stage; the second stage where participants knows the extent of contributions of other participants in the group, in particular whether the other participants have contributed a large (a), medium (b) or small (c) amount; the third stage participants knows to greater details the extent of contributions of other participants in the group, in particular whether the other participants have contributed a very large (a), large (b), medium (c), small (d or very small (e) amount.

Each figure shows three sets of results (squares with dashed lines), what we call Control, Treated and Treatment. In turn, these are:

- Control: the average contribution of participants who are asked to express their contribution to a common pool when this would benefit the general population;
- Treated: the average contribution of participants who are asked to express their contribution to a common pool when this would also benefit a specific vulnerable group, which is different in each city/context;
- Treatment: the difference between the control and treatment average contributions.

You will notice the treatment squares and dashed line lie at the bottom of each Figure and near the zero line. For each of these Treatment squares we also show the confidence intervals, with

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upper and lower bounds. When the line that joins the upper and lower bounds crosses the zero line, then the results are not significant (i.e. significantly different from zero): there is no significant difference between the average contribution when the common pool aims to benefit the general population and the average contribution when it aims to also benefit a specific (targetted) vulnerable group.

Another point to note is about the use of terms. In what follows we will use common pool, common pool resources and public good interchangeably. Sometimes we will be more specific and refer to the exact type of activity or intervention in the city - for instance, the multifunctional green space in Cordoba. Similarly, we will use the terms targeted groups, vulnerable groups - or the specific group in the city, such as the Roma population in Nitra or the Las Palmeras residents in Cordoba - interchangeably. Finally, we will also use the terms cooperation and willingness to contribute to the common pool interchangeably.

5.2. Public good games in the four IN-HABIT cities

5.2.1. Cordoba

The behavioural game in Cordoba was designed to understand how residents feel towards the IN-HABIT project of inclusive **multifunctional green space near Las Palmeras**. The vulnerable group was defined in terms of ethnic or social origin, and included **Las Palmeras residents**.

114 participants took part in the games: 58% were women; the average age was 42, with only 9% of participants identifying as Las Palmeras residents; 76% had a university degree; the average monthly income of participants was €1219.

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Overall cooperation

Figure 3 shows that average contributions are high, participants willing to contribute almost three quarters of their initial endowment to a common pool that is devoted to a multifunctional green space that benefits either the general population or also the specific residents of Las Palmeras. The contribution is slightly less when the common-pool resource benefits Las Palmeras residents than the general population, but the difference is not statistically significant. When looking at dynamic effects, contributions are quite stable over stages and group contributions, especially among participants contributing to a common-pool resource benefitting Las Palmeras residents. In stage 2, and more so in stage 3, participants decrease their contribution once they know the contributions from others is relatively small, particularly in the case of a multifunctional green space that benefits the general population, while they keep the contributions at the same level when the multifunctional green space benefits Las Palemeras' residents.

Overall, cooperation is quite high and does not seem to be affected by the most likely beneficiary's identity. If anything, knowing that the green space also benefits the residents of Las Palmeras is associated with participants maintaining the level of their contribution even when the group contribution decreases. This could be a reflection of a mix of patience and trust, but, overall, it is quite consistent with other research (Falk et al. 2018) that reports a Spanish context where prosociality is quite prominent relative to other European countries.

This is also consistent with post-games discussions with the IN-HABIT team in Cordoba, who pointed out the generally pro-social attitudes of the Cordoba people and, in particular, how Las Palmeras has become, more recently, the neighbourhood of choice for people who want to actively manifest their pro-sociality and community spirit. This may also be a reflection of the extensive communication and programme of activities associated with the IN-HABIT project in Las Palmeras.

Figure 3: Overall average contributions - Cordoba

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Gender gap in cooperation

When decomposing the results by gender, both women and men exert similar behaviours. Knowing the identity of the most likely beneficiary does not change behaviours along the gender dimension. If any, women may be slightly harsher than men in decreasing their contributions once they know others contribute a small amount and when the common-pool

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resource benefits the general population (77 to 63 compared to 80 to 71). Overall, the forgiving pattern described earlier seems to be a common trait among citizens rather than a specific gender feature.

Figure 4: Average contributions, women - Cordoba

Figure 5: Average contributions, men - Cordoba

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Strategies

Although citizens in Cordoba tend to show high levels of cooperation, they do it in very different ways. The group of activists represents quite a large share, almost 40%, of the participants: the unconditional cooperators 22.5% and the compensating contributors 17.1%. Followers add up to 25.2%, and the remaining 35.1% is represented by participants who have

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inconsistent behaviours, or strategies that cannot be categorised within the other three above. This again provides a strong basis for cooperation, consistent with the pattern described above and the characteristics of the context.

When looking at the sociodemographic profiles of these different cooperators, unconditional cooperators are 49% more likely to be men, and are, on average, older (51 years old) and richer (1560€ average monthly income) than the rest of the sample. Conditional cooperators, on the contrary, are, on average, younger (35.6 years old), and do not reside in Las Palmeras, a trait they share with compensating contributors. Inconsistent behaviours are 28% more likely to be women, poorer individuals (1051€ average monthly income), and 3.5 times more likely to be from Las Palmeras.

When put together, these figures highlight potential avenues for improvement. First, in terms of relative size, conditional cooperators and compensating contributors are totalling around 42%. This is a substantive number of contributors reacting to what others are doing. They may be willing to contribute but they need to know about the group contribution to do so. Since both are not living in Las Palmeras, there is a need to communicate about the common-pool resource outside of Las Palmeras. In addition, the conditional cooperators being relatively more numerous, the compensating contributors may not fully compensate for a potential lower interest from the conditional cooperators.

Second, the larger group of participants is the one displaying inconsistent behaviours. They may have conflicting reasons to contribute. Since they are more likely to live in Las Palmeras, they may have difficulties to perceive what value the common-pool resource may have in their neighbourhood, where public services are already lacking or poorly maintained. Therefore, the conflict could arise between their willingness to support the common-pool and their expectation of how it will be maintained.

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5.2.2. Riga

The behavioural game in Riga was designed to understand how residents feel towards the IN-HABIT project of building an **inclusive community stage in Agenskalns market**. The vulnerable group was defined in terms of **sexual minorities**.

108 individuals participated in the experiment: 84% of them were women; 20% defined themselves as belonging to a sexual minority; 66% had a university degree; the average age was 37 and the average income was €1075.

Overall cooperation

Figure 6 shows that average initial contributions are relatively high for both types of public goods: 75 in the case of a pool that explicitly benefits sexual minorities and 85 in the case it is just for the general population. Therefore, participants contribute about 10% less on average when the project benefits sexual minorities than when it benefits everyone. Participants' contribution increases slightly when they know others have contributed a large amount to the project (78 and 84 respectively at stage 2 (a), and decreases when others have contributed a smaller amounts (stage 2 (b and c), and this pattern is the same regardless of whether the project benefits the general population or specific groups.

Figure 6: Overall average contributions - Riga

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Gender gap in cooperation

Figures 7 and 8 report the average contributions for men and women respectively. Men report much higher initial contributions than women if the common pool benefits the general population, but slightly lower if the common pool benefits sexual minorities. Moreover, men tend to decrease their contributions much more substantially than women when they know that others have contributed smaller amounts to the common pool and particularly so when this aims to benefit the general population rather than a sexual minority.

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Figure 7: Average contributions, men - Riga

Figure 8: Average contributions , women - Riga

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Strategies

In assessing strategic behaviours, we find that almost 13% can be categorised as unconditional cooperators, individuals who are committed to the project regardless of what other participants do. We find that men are much more likely than women to be in this group, and this is also the case for relatively well off individuals, with an income almost 60% above the average income of the sample. 7.5% of participants can be categorised as compensating contributors, those

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who are willing to step up and contribute to the common pool if this would be at risk. These are relatively younger compared to the sample average age and none in this category identify as belonging to a sexual minority. Just above a third of participants can be categorised as conditional cooperators, those who follow the rest and decrease their contributions if others do so. These are also relatively younger and half as likely to identify themselves as belonging to a sexual minority. Participants with inconsistent strategies are relatively older on average (39.4 years old).

Overall, on one hand, there appears to be a good proportion of individuals who are very keen on the project regardless of what others do: they contribute the maximum to the common pool in every circumstance. Alongside those who are keen to step up in case, this represents a very good foundation for the sustainability of the project and a reflection, perhaps of the positive image that the project may have conveyed on participants, who are visitors to the market. On the other hand, there appears to be resistance to cooperation when the common pool is explicitly aiming to target sexual minorities: there is, overall, willingness to give less for a targeted intervention than for a generalised one.

5.2.3. Lucca

The behavioural game in Lucca was designed to understand how residents feel towards the IN-HABIT project of inclusive **Animal Assisted Interventions near the Animal Line**. The vulnerable group was defined in terms of age, and included **elderly people (above 65 years old)**.

121 participants took part in the games: 55% were women; the average age was 40, with only 7% of participants being elderly; 51% had a university degree; the average monthly income of participants was €1275.

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Overall cooperation

Figure 9 shows the average contribution of participants to the Lucca experiment. Overall, contributions to the common pool are high relative to what is generally found in public good experiments. Moreover, participants tend to contribute more to the common pool when they know this is also for the specific benefit of old people than when it is for the general population.

Figure 9: Overall average contributions- Lucca

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The contribution also increases when they know others have contributed a relatively large amount. Contributions tend to decline when participants know others have contributed relatively little to the common pool but the decline is much less pronounced when the common pool aims to benefit the elderly. Contributions tend to remain relatively strong, therefore, when participants know that the common pool will go towards a project for the elderly and when they know others have contributed a relatively smaller amount.

Gender gap in cooperation

Women tend to contribute to the common pool more than men, and particularly so when the project benefits the elderly, as shown in **Figures 10 and 11**. This could well be a reflection of established gendered patterns in caring activities and roles. They also tend to increase their contribution when they know that others have given relatively large amounts, but decrease them when they know others have contributed smaller amounts. Men, instead, report a more stable pattern of contributions, not changing much nor decreasing their contribution when they know others have contributed relatively small amounts, particularly so when the project is specifically targeted towards the elderly.

Figure 10: Average contributions, men - Lucca

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Figure 11: Average contributions, women - Lucca

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Strategies

The analysis of strategic behaviours in the Lucca experiment shows a very small proportion (3.5%) of individuals who can be categorised as unconditional contributors. The compensating contributors, the other category of individuals who can be seen as relatively more positive about the project, represent 12.4%. The majority of these two groups - and for the unconditional cooperators, all of them - are participants with a university degree. The conditional cooperators, those who decrease their contributions to the common pool knowing

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that others have also deceased it, are a substantial proportion (40%), of whom more than half are likely to be women than men and have a slightly smaller income than the average for the sample. Participants playing inconsistent strategies constitute the largest group (44.2%). They are more likely to be male (56%), older (41.1 years old on average, also because they are more likely to be above 65 years old (14%)), richer (1415€ average monthly income), and less likely to get a university degree (58%).

Overall, although there is support for a common pool that targets the elderly, and this support is particularly strong amongst women, there is relatively limited unreserved commitment towards it. In addition, women appear to be followers, they follow what others do and if they do not contribute, they do not either. Of course, this may reflect a wide range of contextual factors, including established gendered norms toward caring roles but also potential lack of visibility and/or participation and engagement towards the IN-HABIT project and/or as the focus of activity chosen for the experiment.

Discussion with the INHABIT team in Lucca post experiments also pointed to the traditional Lucca's socio-political context, which combines a strong individualism - reflection of a mercantilist tradition - with an equally strong religious approach towards what is common and shared.

5.2.4. Nitra

The behavioural game in Nitra was designed to understand how residents feel towards the IN-HABIT project of inclusive **picnic meadow near Dražovce**. The vulnerable group was defined in terms of ethnic or social origin, and included **Roma people**.

131 participants took part in the games: 65% were women; the average age was 36, with only 1.5% of participants openly identifying themselves as Roma; 63% had a university degree; the average monthly income of participants was €708.

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Overall cooperation

Figure 12 shows that initial contributions to the common pool are high (76), although there is no difference between the average contribution for a common pool that benefits the targeted Roma groups and one the contribution for a pool that benefits the whole population. It is interesting to note that the initial contribution to the common pool at each stage (stages 1, 2a, 3a) is very similar whether the beneficiary is the general population or the Roma community (between 76 and 78). Participants seem to be able to ignore the most likely beneficiary's identity. Given the relatively high level of contributions, this is a rather good signal for cooperation, though a very fragile one.

The figure also shows how individuals reacted once they know what others in the groups have contributed to. In this case, participants tend to increase their initial contributions once they know others have contributed a relatively orange amount and decrease it when others have contributed relatively little. Moreover, this pattern is more evident when they know the common-pool resource would benefit the Roma community than if they knew it would benefit the general population, although, most of the time, the difference is not statistically significant.

To summarize, there is a small willingness to step-up if the group contributions slightly decrease when the common-pool benefits the Roma community by maintaining the level of contribution, but not much forgiveness as they tolerate it only at the second stage and even converge to the contribution level for the general population at the last stage.

Figure 12: Overall average contributions - Nitra

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Gender gap in cooperation

When decomposing the results by gender, shown in **Figures 13 and 14**, we can see very different behaviours from women and men. Women tend to contribute more if the common-pool resource benefits the Roma community, though the difference is statistically significant only in stage 2 and stage 3 (**Figure 18**). They slightly increase their contribution when they know that others have contributed a large amount but also decrease it slightly

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when others have done so as well and this is similar whether the beneficiary is the Roma community or the general population.

Figure 13: Average contributions, women - Nitra

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Men, on the other hand, seem to contribute less when the common-pool benefits the Roma community, although the difference is not statistically significant (**Figure 19**). But, the largest gaps in contributions are systematically observed when male participants know that others contribute the most (stage 2a and 3a). When they know that others contribute little, they also reduce their contribution, and this regardless of the beneficiary's identity. This pattern could indicate that men free-ride or try to opt-out when it is the easiest (or most beneficial) to do so. However, patterns in stage 3 seem to reveal that men only start reducing their contributions when the group contributions are lower than a medium amount.

Figure 14: Average contributions, men - Nitra

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Overall, gender differences are mostly concentrated when the group contributions are the highest (stage 2a, 3a, and 3b). This is important to note that this difference of behaviours is induced by the most likely beneficiary's identity, although the exact reasons that make women and men behave differently when the Roma community is involved are not known.

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Strategies

Participants in Nitra played different kinds of strategies. Activists account for almost 26% of the participants: unconditional cooperators for 14.5% and compensating contributors for 11.4%. Conditional cooperators represent 35.1%, while the remaining 39% are made of inconsistent behaviours.

Those reacting to what others are doing are in general younger (31.9 and 30.4 years old for the conditional cooperators and compensating contributors respectively). But they also have specific characteristics. Conditional cooperators tend to be poorer (451€ average monthly income) whereas compensating contributors are not Dražovce residents. Finally, participants playing inconsistent strategies tend to be older (38.9 years old) and richer (907€ average monthly income), while unconditional cooperators do not seem to have any particular characteristics.

Altogether, several potential avenues for improvement emerge. First, almost three quarters of the participants are either conditional cooperators or contributing inconsistently. Support for the project is thus very fragile, and is very likely that the activists would not be able to compensate for the conditional cooperators' potential withdrawal. However, the fact that both the conditional cooperators and compensating contributors are of the same age suggests that it may be possible to target them with the same communication effort. In this regard, promoting non-monetary contributions may be an argument for convincing the conditional cooperators who may be more financially constrained.

Second, the unconditional cooperators do not seem to have any particular characteristics. It makes it very difficult to target and understand the motivation of such a heterogeneous group, especially when they are so critical for a common-pool resource. Similarly, participants with inconsistent behaviours will be difficult to target since they may have very different motivations.

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6. Discussion

The first phase of behavioural games in the four cities of the IN-HABIT project aimed to elicit preferences towards a common pool resource or activity, specifically identified to reflect the local context of the project. The preference elicitation extended not just to assess the extent of contribution to a contextualised common pool - whether a multifunctional green space in Cordoba, a picnic meadow in Nitra, an inclusive community stage in Aogenskalns market or animal assisted interventions near the Animal Line in Lucca - but also to assess whether the contribution to the common pool differed when the identified common pool benefitted a specific vulnerable group: the residents of Las Palmeras in Cordoba, the Roma community in the Drazovce neighbourhood of Nitra, sexual minorities in Riga and elderly people in Lucca. Furthermore, the experiments assessed whether the contributions to a common pool differed when the participants knew what others in the group contributed to.

We found that the average contributions to a common pool, however this is defined, is relatively high in our four experiments compared to typical levels reported in the literature: in most cases, individuals are willing to contribute to a public good around three-quarters of their initial endowment. It is possible that this relatively high willingness to contribute to a common pool reflects the fact that the common pool has very specific and clearly-defined aims and objective and target beneficiaries.

Despite this common finding across cities, we found differences between the four cities in contributions by gender, the extent of contributions when the project was identified as benefitting the vulnerable groups or the general population, and the extent of reaction to contributions when participants knew what others were contributing towards the common pool.

We also found some differences between the cities in the extent of strategic behaviours and “commitment” towards the common pool. For instance, the experiment in Cordoba revealed a relatively large proportion (more than 22%) of unconditional cooperators, those who would be

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contributing to the common pool regardless of what others would do, while this proportion is relatively small in Lucca (3.5%). When considered alongside the proportion of those who are willing to compensate for deceased contributions from others - and therefore also keen to ensure the sustainability of the common pool - we found the overall “commitment” to the public good (combination of unconditional cooperators and compensating contributors) ranges from 40% in Cordoba to 16% in Lucca. This could well be a reflection of various factors we are not able to assess here; post experiments discussions with the IN-HABIT cities partners all refer to local contexts, whether cultural, political and historical, but could also reflect the specific type of public good and target beneficiary group identified in each city. These differences make comparisons between cities difficult.

These results, however, also show that a relative majority of participants are followers, namely they contribute to the same extent as others in the group do, once they know it. The extent of this differs between the cities but, overall, suggests that the sustainability of the common pool resource does not stand on very solid ground, that cooperation is not given and needs to be nurtured and sustained. Each city and context will have different approaches and solutions to this issue and to ensure that the proportion of those who are committed to the project, and ideally those who are unconditional cooperators is maximised. However, a common high-level approach would rely on sustained and improved campaigns that advocate and communicate the benefits of the project and activity.

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Annexes

1. Description of the common-pool resources

a. Cordoba

It is a green area where you can walk, do outdoor activities, carry out collective or artistic initiatives, walk with pets or do environmental activities and activities to improve mental and physical health. This space combines two leisure and socialization areas (with benches, tables and equipment) through a path developed with materials sustainable, permeable soils and native vegetation that provides shade. It is accessible to everyone and has benches designed to sit in a group along the path and be able to chat or perform concentration and relaxation exercises, and it is specially designed to be a safe and protected space for women who decide to walk through said area, with public lighting adapted to the environment and signage.

b. Riga

This game is about investing in a community stage. It is a platform where the amateur and professional organizations, as well as local citizens of the neighbourhood, are able to offer and perform their initiatives in various forms to broaden the cultural exchange and accessibility of diverse knowledge and experiences. The community stage is planned in the outdoor territory as a wooden platform with roof and applied area around it with or without tables and chairs for visitors (depending on the format of the event).

c. Lucca

This game is about investing in activities with animals that aim to improve relationships between humans, and between humans and animals, and improve health and well-being.

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These activities will take place in fenced areas equipped with shaded spaces and benches, called "Relational Areas" which will be built in the River Park along the Animal Lines. To make them accessible to anyone, even those who don't have pets, professionals will organize specific educational and recreational play events with their appropriately trained animals. The activities could, for example, consist of throwing a dog's "treat" into a container and, if it hits the mark, the dog can be sent to fetch it.

d. Nitra

2. Framing

a. Cordoba

Control condition:

At the moment, this is a preliminary project that could come to life in the coming months somewhere in the city of Córdoba.

Treatment condition:

At the moment, this is a preliminary project that could come to life in the coming months in the neighbourhood of Las Palmeras de Córdoba, a vulnerable area of social transformation.

b. Riga

Control condition:

At the moment, this community stage is a preliminary project that could come to life in the coming months in the Agenskalns neighbourhood. Although you won't be asked to contribute financially to the realization of the final project, the decision you will make in this game should

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reflect your willingness to engage with the project. The project will benefit the entire community with general audience events.

Treatment condition:

At the moment, this community stage is a preliminary project that could come to life in the coming months in the Agenskalns neighbourhood. Although you won't be asked to contribute financially to the realization of the final project, the decision you will make in this game should reflect your willingness to engage with the project. The project will benefit the entire community with general audience events, but will welcome in particular events aimed at fostering the inclusion of sexual minorities.

c. Lucca

Control condition:

At the moment, activities with animals are at a preliminary stage and could come to life in the coming months. Although you won't be asked to contribute financially to the realization of the final project, the decision you will make in this game should reflect your willingness to engage with the project. The project will benefit the entire community with its recreational and educational activities with animals.

Treatment condition:

At the moment, activities with animals are at a preliminary stage and could come to life in the coming months. Although you won't be asked to contribute financially to the realization of the final project, the decision you will make in this game should reflect your willingness to engage with the project. The project will benefit the entire community with its recreational and educational activities with animals, but initiatives aimed at the inclusion of the elderly (>65 years) will be developed in particular.

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d. Nitra

3. Pay-offs structure

Participants get 100 tokens at the beginning of each stage to invest in the common-pool resource. At Stage 1, they are simply asked how many of those 100 tokens they want to invest in the common-pool resource. At Stage 2, they are asked how many of their 100 tokens they want to invest given how much their group would have invested at the previous stage. The amount invested by the group is hypothetical and could be one of the three scenarios proposed, (a) a large, (b) medium, or (c) small amount. At Stage 3, they repeat the same process as Stage 2, but, this time, given what their group would have invested at the previous two stages. We can describe this structure with the following tree:

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Participants used the following forms to fill their choices:

Now, please answer to all of the three different situations marked (a), (b), (c).

Total tokens invested in Stage 1 by your group	How many tokens you invest at stage 2 (0-100)
(a) High: >300	_____
(b) Medium: 200-300	_____
(c) Low: <200	_____

For this third stage, we ask you to invest tokens depending on how many tokens other members of the group have invested over stage 1 & stage 2. *Please answer to all of the five different situations marked (a), (b), (c), (d) and (e), as you previously did in stage 2.*

Total tokens invested by your group – Stage 1 + Stage 2	How many tokens you invest at stage 3 (0-100)
(a) Very High: >800	_____
(b) High: 600-800	_____
(c) Medium: 400-600	_____
(d) Low: 200-400	_____
(e) Very Low: <200	_____

The final pay-offs from the game are composed of a part coming from their contribution to the common-pool and the tokens they kept for themselves. The game generated a pay-off equal to triple the group contribution, then divided equally among the five members of each group. Finally, a fixed amount covering for participation fees was added on top of their pay-offs from the game.

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Participants were provided with the following example:

“For example, if you invest 240 tokens over the 3 stages and that, when added to the other amount invested of the group, you sum up 1200 tokens altogether over the 3 stages, you will each receive a gain of 720 tokens ($1200 \cdot 3/5$ participants) in addition to your participation fee and what remains from your game endowment (300-260 tokens), so 42€ euros total (780 tokens = 23€ from the game + 19€). We provide another detailed example below.”

Groups were formed randomly posterior to the game. If the total number of participants was not a multiple of five, we would randomly select the number of missing participants in the pool of already matched participants. These participants would be duplicated to complete the groups and be able to compute pay-offs on the same basis for every participant. We then used the realized contributions at Stage 1 to determine the group contributions at Stage 2 and 3.

All amounts were adjusted using 2019 real terms labour productivity to provide comparable incentives to participants across cities. To do so, we use the closest local estimates using the nominal labour productivity and price level index for final household consumption expenditures for the year 2019 at the NUTS 3 level. Both datasets are from Eurostat. They were the latest data of this kind at the time of the design of the experiment. In the end, participation fees ranged between 16€ and 26€, endowments were equivalent to between 8€ and 13€ with maximum pay-offs between 40€ and 65€.

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